

Web-Based Quality of Life Data Collection: A Review in Radiation Oncology

Ian Messing¹, Sharad Goyal, MD², Martin Ojong-Ntui, MD², Yuan J. Rao, MD²

¹George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences, ²Division of Radiation Oncology, George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences

Correspondence should be directed to:

Yuan J. Rao, MD

Radiation Oncology

George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences

2150 Pennsylvania Ave NW

Washington, DC 20037

(202) 715-5097

yrao@mfa.gwu.edu

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Summary

The current healthcare environment places significant emphasis on patient quality of life. This is particularly important in radiation oncology as the side-effects of radiation therapy can develop over time. Routine quality of life assessments can place additional burden on both patients and providers, with the potential to disrupt clinical workflow. Properly implemented electronic quality of life assessments could work as a medium to conveniently and efficiently administer, collect, and analyze patient responses.

Abstract

The current healthcare climate places significant emphasis on patient quality of life (QoL). This is particularly important in radiation oncology as the side effects of radiation therapy may develop over months or years. With this in mind, many providers are incorporating regular QoL assessments into their practice. However, routine QoL assessments can place additional burden on both patients and providers, with the potential to disrupt clinical workflow. Properly implemented, electronic QoL assessments could efficiently administer, collect, and analyze patient responses. The system must be designed to enhance data quality and compliance while maintaining protection of patient information at the forefront of all design efforts. This research letter presents a brief overview of our method for designing and implementing a web-based QoL questionnaire and repository for use in our clinic using Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap, Vanderbilt University). REDCap is a noncommercial, secure, and HIPAA-compliant web-based platform. Using branching logic and data validation tools we were able to pilot the electronic QoL assessment for our head and neck cancer patients using the EORTC Quality of Life Group's core questionnaire, the EORTC QLQ-C30, and the EORTC QLQ-H&N35. As the REDCap project was designed to limit patient decision-making and effort, once initiated by a team member, the electronic QoL assessment can be completed by the patient without additional assistance or supervision. We outline the preliminary steps of creating and applying a simple yet effective electronic repository using an accessible and customizable collection platform.

Introduction

Patient quality of life (QoL) significantly impacts methods of healthcare delivery. Radiation oncology providers regularly incorporate QoL assessments into their practice to assess treatment toxicities and late effects of therapy. However, routine QoL assessments may burden patients and providers and potentially disrupt clinical workflow.¹

Electronic QoL assessment systems mitigate obstacles to collecting and analyzing patient data.² These challenges include potential poor handling of paper forms, transcription errors during analysis, and lack of validation checks.^{2,3} Electronic collection systems provide an efficient and convenient means to the same end. To maximize effectiveness, these platforms must be implemented in a logical manner and emphasize protection of patient information.

In this research letter, we outline our method for designing and implementing a web-based QoL questionnaire and repository in our clinic.⁴ We also outline steps to build an effective system for patient data collection using a manageable technique.

Platform

In partnership with Children's National Hospital, our institution provides Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) to easily build online surveys and databases.⁵ REDCap is a noncommercial, secure, and HIPAA-compliant web-based platform developed by Vanderbilt University. This fast and flexible program can be used to export data to common data analysis packages and create custom ad hoc reports. REDCap functions on our institution's local server and communicates with Vanderbilt University's server for specialized auto-scoring and computerized adaptive testing (CAT) functionality. REDCap's infrastructure requirements and dependencies include a web server with PHP (Personal Home Page), a MySQL (My Structured Query Language) database server, a SMTP (Simple

Mail Transfer Protocol) e-mail server, and a file server. Our institution leverages a dedicated team at Children's National Hospital to manage these servers.

Questionnaire

REDCap users can create custom questionnaires or download existing questionnaires from a shared online library. Our institution utilizes the EORTC Quality of Life Group's core questionnaire, the EORTC QLQ-C30 (QLQ30), and site-specific modules to assess QoL of patients who received treatment for head and neck cancer (HNC), endometrial cancer, and cervical cancer. We also utilize the International Prostate Symptom Score (I-PSS) and the Sexual Health Inventory for Men (SHIM) survey to assess QoL of patients who received treatment for prostate cancer.

The EORTC QLQ-H&N35 (H&N35) is a widely used tool to measure QoL in HNC patients.⁶ It contains multi- and single-item scales to assess several patient domains. While the H&N35 presents some methodological problems, it has been successfully implemented in clinical practice and validated in large-scale studies.⁷ We recreated a version of both the QLQ30 and the H&N35 in REDCap.

Project Setup

The project was designed using longitudinal data collection. Due to variations in type and frequency of patient encounters, we define events by patients' unique medical record numbers (MRN) and type of encounter. Combined with the assessment date, we can analyze patient encounters over time.

A team member initiates patient encounters by accessing REDCap, providing the patient's MRN, and selecting the visit type (Figure 1). To access the H&N35, team members indicate that they are preparing a subsequent follow-up visit for an HNC patient.

Based on the visit type, the project is designed with branching logic to queue a validation survey where patients provide their initials and date of birth. We included this step

to validate the response collection and to familiarize patients with the platform before initiating the QoL survey (Figure 2). Upon completion, the patient will be presented with the QLQ30 and then the H&N35 (Figure 3). The patient is notified once each survey is complete and is asked to continue until all components of the branching sequence have been fulfilled.

At the inception of this project we uploaded 23 completed H&N35 questionnaires for the assessment of patients recovering from radiation therapy for HNC to our institution's electronic medical record (EMR). Once the project was created, we piloted this web-based tool using these questionnaires.

Data Quality and Compliance

The project was designed to reduce patient decision-making and effort. After initiating the patient encounter, branching logic and queues administer the validation tool and subsequent QoL surveys.

Survey sections are displayed as matrices of fields and separated over different web pages when answer choices or response prompts change (Figure 4). This design was implemented to limit patient confusion and promote data quality and compliance.

When forms were completed by hand, some patients did not complete the survey or selected multiple responses for a given question. As such, data validation techniques are employed to ensure appropriate completion of each survey.

Patient Encounter

After checking in at our clinic, a team member escorts the patient to an examination room. The team member accesses the project in REDCap and enters initial patient information. Next, the team member assesses the completion of the initial validation survey. When completed, the first questionnaire is selected and opened. The patient uses a laptop computer to complete the QoL surveys queued in the web-browser (Figure 5). Team members are notified via email that patients' responses are complete and have been

collected. Importantly, the responses of patients who could not navigate the web-based platform can be manually collected and uploaded to the project retrospectively.

Discussion

Development of a simple and effective web-based platform for survey administration presents many challenges. The REDCap program facilitated this objective by enabling efficient administration of web-based surveys. The QLQ30 and H&N35 were foundational starting points upon which to expand our platform and assess other treatment sites. We will also use the platform to administer I-PSS and SHIM surveys, comment on patient initial visits, and report on patient deaths. Further, given the simplicity of the REDCap platform, we have successfully administered surveys on tablet computers and aim to expand their use in our clinic.⁸

REDCap is currently unable to interface with our institution's EMR so a team member must use another system to assess recent patient responses. However, REDCap enables data export to common data analysis packages and creation of custom ad hoc reports. This feature, with its simplicity and flexibility, makes REDCap an ideal platform to overcome challenges previously associated with QoL assessment and analysis.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1: The patient encounter is initiated by a team member entering the MRN and selecting a reason for the encounter. For HNC patients, the team member would select “Subsequent Follow-Up QoL Head and Neck Cancer.”

Figure 2: The patient is asked to provide their initials and date of birth in a brief validation survey. This serves to validate the collection of the responses and to familiarize patients with the platform.

Figure 3: The project was designed with branching logic to transition patients through the desired QoL assessments. Patients with HNC will progress through identification, verification, QLQ30, and H&N35.

Figure 4: Matrix fields were utilized to limit patient confusion and promote data quality and compliance. This was achieved by grouping items with similar prompts and responses. It should be noted that the QLQ30 and H&N35 were not provided in their entirety in compliance with user agreements with the EORTC Quality of Life Group.

Figure 5: Surveys were queued based on the designed branching logic. In this instance, H&N35 would be queued upon completion of QLQ30 and upon selection of “Subsequent Follow-Up QoL Head and Neck Cancer” (initial selection 6) by the team member.

Participant ID	<input type="text"/>
Medical Record Number (MRN):	<input type="text"/>
<small>* must provide value</small>	
Please Select from the Following Options:	<input type="text"/>
<small>* must provide value</small>	

Figure 1

Please fill in your initials (First and Last):
* must provide value

Your birthdate (DD-MM-YYYY):
* must provide value

 D-M-Y

Today's date (DD-MM-YYYY):
* must provide value

 D-M-Y

Figure 2

Data Collection Instruments

Survey options:

Add new instrument:

a new instrument from scratch
 a new instrument from the official [REDCap Shared Library](#)
 instrument ZIP file from another project/user or [external libraries](#)

Instrument name	Fields	View PDF	Enabled as survey	Instrument actions	Survey-related options
Patient Identification	3		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Choose action ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Survey settings + Automated Invitations
Patient Verification	3		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Choose action ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Survey settings + Automated Invitations
Eortc Qlq C30 Version 3	30		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Choose action ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Survey settings + Automated Invitations
EORTC QLQ - H&N35	35		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Choose action ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Survey settings + Automated Invitations

Figure 3

During the past week:			
	No	Yes	
Have you used pain-killers?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	reset
Have you taken any nutritional supplements (excluding vitamins)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	reset
Have you used a feeding tube?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	reset
Have you lost weight?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	reset
Have you gained weight?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	reset

Figure 4

 Activated <input type="button" value="Deactivate"/>	"EORTC QLQ - H&N35"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> When the following survey is completed: <input type="text" value="EORTC QLQ - C30 (version 3)"/> <input type="button" value="AND"/> <input type="button" value="v"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> When the following logic becomes true: How to use this <input type="text" value="[initial_selection] = '6'"/> <small>(e.g., [age] > 30 and [gender] = "1")</small> Test logic with a record: <input type="text" value="-- select record --"/> <input type="button" value="v"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
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Figure 5